

A Study on the Challenges faced by the Women Entrepreneur of Port Blair City

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Introduction :

Women's entrepreneurship needs to be studied separately for two main reasons. The first reason is that women's entrepreneurship has been recognized during the last decade as an important untapped source of economic growth. Women entrepreneurs create new jobs for themselves and others and by being different also provide society with different solutions to management, organization and business problems as well as to the exploitation of entrepreneurial opportunities. However, they still represent a minority of all entrepreneurs. Thus there exists a market failure discriminating against women's possibility to become entrepreneurs and their possibility to become successful entrepreneurs. This market failure needs to be addressed by policy makers so that the economic potential of this group can be fully utilized.

Objectives of the Study :

1. To discuss the problems faced by women entrepreneurs in India.
2. To study the demographic profile of the respondents.

3. To find out the remedies to improve the state of women entrepreneurship in India.

Measures to Improve Women Entrepreneurship :

Women entrepreneurship in India faces many challenges and requires a radical change in attitudes and mindsets of society. Therefore, programs should be designed to address changes in attitude and mindset of the people. Women of the present times should be made aware regarding her unique identity and her contribution towards the economic growth and development of the country. Course Curriculum should be designed in a manner that will impart the basic theoretical knowledge along with its practical implication and help impart skills required to be an entrepreneur. At the same time, there are various schemes like the Government Sponsored Schemes regarding start-up or World Bank sponsored programmed that can be undertaken for such purposes. Programmes can be conducted in which established and successful women entrepreneurs can advise and warn for the coming women entrepreneurs against the challenges they will face against being entrepreneur to boost the morale and confidence level of the upcoming entrepreneurs. Government should also play an important role by setting up policies and plan that supports entrepreneurship opportunities. Setting up good infrastructure is also required to build entrepreneurship opportunities.

Analysis of Data :

➤ Distribution of Age :

From the below table it is depicts that the majority (37.5%) of the women entrepreneur are comes under the age group of 31-40 years.

Table No. 1

Variables	Class	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	Below 20	2	5
	21-30	13	32.5
	31-40	15	37.5
	41-50	3	7.5
	Above 50	7	17.5
	Total	40	100

Source: Primary Data

➤ **Distribution of Marital Status :**

From the below table it is concluded that a thumbing majority (80%) of the respondents are married women.

Table No. 2

Sl. No.	Variable	Sub- Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Marital Status	Single	5	12.5
2		Married	32	80
3		Widow	3	7.5
		Total	40	100

Source: Primary Data

➤ **Distribution of Education :**

From the below mentioned table it is depicts that a clear majority (75%) of the women entrepreneur are having the education qualification of Higher education.

Table No. 3

Sl. No.	Variable	Sub-Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Education	Illiterate	1	2.5
2		Secondary Education	5	12.5
3		Higher Education	30	75
4		Graduate	3	7.5
5		Post Graduate	1	2.5
		Total	40	100

Source: Primary Data

➤ **Women Entrepreneur Activities :**

It is clearly shows from the below mentioned table that a decent majority (42.5%) of the women entrepreneur are engaged in Tailoring activities.

Table No. 4

Sl. No.	Women entrepreneur Activities	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Beauty Parlour	5	12.5
2	Retailing	13	32.5
3	Street Vending	3	7.5
4	Tailoring	17	42.5
5	Job Typing	2	5
	Total	40	100

Source: Primary Data

➤ **Challenges of Women Entrepreneur :**

It is clearly shows from the below mentioned table that majority (27.5%) of the women entrepreneur are facing the challenges as capital arrangement.

Table No. 5

Sl. No.	Challenge of Women Entrepreneur	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Capital	11	27.5
2	Competition	3	7.5
3	Work and Home	5	12.5
4	Networking	3	7.5
5	Education and Skills	2	5
6	Risk Taking	3	7.5
7	Tradition	1	2.5
8	Technology	7	17.5
9	Access to Markets	5	12.5
	Total	40	100

Source: Primary Data

Conclusion :

The study reveals that women entrepreneur's faces constraints related to access to finance, conflicts between work and family responsibilities, networking

challenges, lack of education and management skills. Though having lot of challenges but the women entrepreneurs are trying their best to overcome from the challenges to boost their business at the early stage.

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